

Chemical Components of *Didymocarpus Pedicellata*

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Didymocarpus pedicellata is a small herbaceous plant growing in the subtropical Western Himalayan region at altitudes of 2,500-5,500 ft. The dried leaves have a characteristic spicy odour and a reddish brown dust on the underside. In this respect these resemble the leaves of *Streptocarpus dunnii*, belonging to the same plant family (Gesneriaceae). Price and Robinson¹ suggested that there might be some relationship between the pigments of the two plants. Actually pedicinin (I) of *D. pedicellata* and dunnione (II) of *S. dunnii* are quinones though belonging to different groups. The leaves of the former keep well on storage and are not attacked by fungi in a humid atmosphere. These leaves have been valued for their medicinal properties² and used in India as a cure for kidney and bladder stones. The main components of the leaves are toxic³ to fish.

(I)

(II)

The chemical investigation of these leaves was first undertaken by Siddiqui⁴ who isolated a number of new compounds. A brief description of these is given below; these have been shown to belong to the group of chalcones and flavanones.

Pedicellin (III) was the first component of the leaves, structure of which was correctly understood. It has the molecular formula C₂₀H₂₂O₆, contains five methoxyl groups, forms a phenylhydrazone, and adds two atoms of bromine. On degradation with alkali or oxidation with potassium permanganate, it yields benzaldehyde (IV). Sharma and Siddiqui⁵ therefore proposed a pentamethoxychalcone structure (III) for pedicellin. This was confirmed by Baker⁶ who synthesised it by condensing pentamethoxyacetophenone (V) and benzaldehyde.

Pedigin (VI) is the most abundant member of the group and it has been shown by Seshadri⁷ that the other compounds of this group could originate from it. The structure

⁷Second Part of the Seventeenth Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture delivered at the National Institute of Sciences Hall, New Delhi, on August 4, 1964 under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society.

1. *Nature*, 1938, 142, 147.

2. Chopra and Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India", 2nd ed., 1958, p. 333.

3. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 27A, 129; 28A, 106.

4. *This Journal*, 1937, 14, 703.

5. *Ibid.*, 1939, 16, 1.

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 663.

7. *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1951, 1, 186.

of pedicin was studied first by Sharma and Siddiqui³. It has the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{16}O_6$ and contains three methoxyl groups. It gave a phenylhydrazone, a dibenzoate, and a dihydro derivative, indicating presence of a carbonyl, two hydroxyl groups, and a double bond. On methylation it yielded pedicellin. Siddiqui⁴ assigned *ortho* positions 2 and 3 for the two hydroxyl groups, based on colour reactions, but Rao and Seshadri⁵ proposed that these were at the *para* positions 2 and 5 (structure VI), based on biogenetic considerations.

The above structure of pedicin was confirmed by its synthesis involving the nuclear oxidation of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxychalcone (VIII) by means of alkaline persulphate. By complete methylation it readily yielded the pentamethoxychalcone (pedicellin) (III); by flavanone ring closure, isopedicin (IX); by mild oxidation, pedicin quinone; and by oxidative demethylation, methylpedicin (X) and pedicin (I). The synthesis of pedicin therefore led also to the synthesis of the various members of the group and to the elucidation of their correct structures. The relationship among the various components of *D. pedicellata* is shown in the following chart.

Fatty Components

In the earlier studies Siddiqui and co-workers⁹ reported the presence of saturated acids which were obtained by saponification of the fatty residue obtained from the ethereal extract of the leaves. These were found to consist of lignoceric (XI), behenic (XII), stearic (XIII), and palmitic (XIV) acids in nearly equal proportion; they also stated that stearic acid was present in the acidic fraction of the original extract, but none of the other saturated acids.

(XI), $n = 22$

(XII), $n = 20$

(XIII), $n = 16$

(XIV), $n = 14$

Recently, Rao, Seshadri, and Scod¹⁰ have reported the isolation of a new dicarboxylic acid from the ether extract of the leaves by shaking it with sodium bicarbonate solution. On acidification, the clear alkaline solution yielded a deep brown solid which was a mixture of pedicinin and the new dicarboxylic acid. Much of the former could be separated by crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum mixture. Chromatography of the crude acid on cellulose column did not effect further purification, but repeated recrystallisation from carbon tetrachloride-light petroleum mixture and finally from aqueous ethanol furnished the pure acid in colorless silky needles. It has been named *pedicellic acid*.

Constitution of Pedicellic Acid

Pedicellic acid melts at 92-93°. Its elemental analysis corresponds to the empirical formula $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4$ and it does not contain any functional group other than the carboxyl. The ultraviolet spectrum does not show any characteristic absorption. The infrared spectrum has the following characteristic bands. A strong absorption at 1709 cm^{-1} can be assigned to an acid carboxyl and the band at 2941 cm^{-1} is diagnostic of methylene groups. The absorption at 720 cm^{-1} can be regarded as due to a chain of four or more methylene groups. These indicate that pedicellic acid is a long-chain aliphatic acid. The number of carboxylic groups has been determined by conductometric titration with sodium metathoxide; the nature of the curve is comparable with that of oxalic acid or of other acids, containing two carboxyl groups of identical nature. Volumetric titration using a non-aqueous medium shows that its equivalent weight is between 154 and 160; therefore its molecular weight should be between 308 and 320. Pedicellic acid appeared therefore to be an aliphatic dicarboxylic acid of the molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$.

Several aliphatic dicarboxylic acids have been known to occur in plants¹¹. Some like traumatic acid have been considered to have hormonal properties (wound hormones). A list of these with essential data is shown in Table I

9. *This Journal*, 1939, 18, 423.

10. Paper read in "International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Product", Tokyo, 1964.

11. Taket *et al.*, *Chem. Zvest.*, 1940, II, 3391.

TABLE I

S. No.	Name of the acid.	Source.
A. Saturated.		
1.	Aselaic acid (XV)	Pyrethrum extract ¹¹
2.	Sebacic acid (XVI)	Yeast ¹²
3.	Thapsic acid (XVII)	<i>Thapsia gargatica</i> ¹³
4.	Nonadecanoic acid (XVIII)	<i>Rhus succedanea</i> ¹⁴
5.	Eicosmic acid (XIX)	<i>Rhus succedanea</i> ¹⁵
6.	Japenic acid (XX)	<i>Rhus succedanea</i> ¹⁶
7.	Phellogenic acid (XXI)	<i>Rhus coriaria</i> (<i>stra</i>) ¹⁷
8.	Heneicosan dicarboxylic acid (XXII)	<i>Rhus succedanea</i> ¹⁷
	HOOC — (CH ₂) _n — COOH	
	(XV), n = 7	(XIX), n = 18
	(XVI), n = 8	(XX), n = 19
	(XVII), n = 14	(XXI), n = 21
	(XVIII), n = 17	(XXII), n = 22
B. Unsaturated.		
(i)	Dec-2-en-1,10-dioic acid (XXIII)	<i>Penicillium notatum</i> ¹⁸
(ii)	Traumatic acid (XXIV)	Bean pods ¹⁹
(iii)	Octadec-9-en-1,18-dioic acid (XXV)	Cork ²⁰
(iv)	Dec-2,8 diene-4,8-diyne-1,10-dioic acid (XXVI)	<i>Polyporus anthracophilus</i> ²¹
	HOOC—CH = CH—(CH ₂) ₆ —COOH (XXIII)	
	HOOC—CH = CH—(CH ₂) ₈ —COOH (XXIV)	
	HOOC—CH ₂ —CH = CH—(CH ₂) ₇ —COOH (XXV)	
	HOOC—CH = CH—C ≡ C—C ≡ C—CH = CH—COOH (XXVI)	

There was no agreement between the properties of any of these acids with pedicellie acid; its melting point was too low for its molecular size. At this stage it was found that pedicellie acid showed a marked fluorescein test, indicating the presence of succinic or glutaric acid system in it. It could be converted into the corresponding anhydride (XXVII) in two different ways. The acid was first treated with dicyclohexylcarbodi-imide when a quantitative yield of dicyclohexylurea was obtained by the ready elimination of a molecule of water. This dehydration is possible according to Khorana²² if the acid has the skeleton:

where $n=1, 2, 3$, or 4 . Pedicellie acid may therefore be a malonic, succinic, glutaric, or adipic acid derivative. The other product of the reaction was an anhydride, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_5$. The same anhydride was obtained by the acetic anhydride-pyridine method. The

12. Kuhn and Schwarz, *Ber.*, 1941, 74, 1617.
13. Ganzmerl, *Ber.*, 1884, 17.
14. Schaal, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4784.
15. Shima, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1941, I, 140.
16. Geitel and Van der Want, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1900 *ii*, 81, 151.
17. Tsubimoto, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, I, 1544, 1545.
18. Oram and Tishler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4238.
19. English *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 3434.
20. Ribas and Becano, *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 806.
21. Bullock *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 696.
22. *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 145.

formation of a stable anhydride and a positive fluorescein test indicate that pedicellio acid is either a succinic acid or a glutaric acid derivative.

Based on the above data and on the two probable alternatives of succinic or glutaric acid units, pedicellio acid could be represented by any one of the formulae: (XXXIII):

(XXVIII) to (XXXII):

(XXX) to (XXXIII):

At this stage the data provided by NMR spectrum came in quite useful. The NMR spectrum of the dimethyl ester of pedicellio acid has been found to have the following characteristic signals. A peak at 6.38 τ has been assigned to the protons of the ester groups. As it has been proved by conductometric titration that pedicellio acid is a dicarboxylic acid, there is no doubt that its dimethyl ester should contain six protons and the intensity of this signal should correspond to this number of protons. A peak at 8.65 τ has been assigned to methylene groups and the integrated intensity of this peak corresponds to about 24 protons. Two signals at 9.15 τ and 9.25 τ (3 protons each) represented two *C*-methyl groups of nonidentical nature. The signal at 9.15 τ corresponds to the terminal methyl group of a long aliphatic chain, whereas signal at 9.25 τ to the methyl of propionic acid residue having substitution at the α -position. The total number of protons present in the acid is 34 which agrees with the molecular formula already arrived at. These data eliminated a number of possibilities and indicated that the structure of pedicellio acid was that of an α - α' -disubstituted succinic acid (XXXIV). This has been established by further chemical evidences (*vide infra*).

Pedicellic acid has been converted into the corresponding hydrocarbon (XXXV) *Pedicellane* by the following reactions²³. It was first esterified by refluxing it in a mixture of absolute methanol and dry benzene containing concentrated sulphuric acid. Reduction of the dimethyl ester (XXXVI) with lithium aluminium hydride, employing the conditions of Downing *et al.*²³, afforded the corresponding diol (a 1,4-butane diol) (XXXVII), elemental analysis of which corresponded to the formula $C_{16}H_{36}O_2$. Its infrared spectrum shows a weak band at 3400 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of primary alcoholic groups. A strong absorption band at 2985 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 720 cm^{-1} are diagnostic of methylene groups.

The diol (XXXVII), on treatment with iodine and red phosphorus, yielded a di-iodide (XXXVIII) which on reduction with LiAlH_4 afforded a hydrocarbon (XXXV) whose analysis corresponded to $C_{16}H_{36}$. The infrared spectrum includes all the characteristic peaks for an aliphatic hydrocarbon, but the hydrocarbon does not agree with any known hydrocarbon of C_{16} skeleton.

The nature of pedicellic acid as a succinic acid having substituents on both methylene C-atoms and the identity of the substituent groups were established by the following sequence of reactions. Pedicellic acid was treated with hydrazoic acid ($\text{NaN}_3, \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$), employing the procedure of Schmid²⁴, when the corresponding diamine (XXXIX) was obtained. A solution of it (XXXIX) in concentrated hydrochloric acid was treated at 5° with a saturated solution of sodium nitrite, whereby the corresponding C_{16} glycol (1,2-diol; XL) was produced. This was subjected to periodic acid oxidation. The volatile fragment obtained in the steam distillate was characterised as acetaldehyde (XLI) through its 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

The nonvolatile fraction was oxidised to the corresponding acid (XLII), using alkaline potassium permanganate, and it was found to be myristic acid.

23. *Austri. J. Chem.*, 1960, 13, 80.

24. Schmid, "Org. Reaction", Vol. 13, p. 307.

Pedicellic acid (XLIII) therefore is very similar to roccellic acid (XLIV), commonly found in lichens²⁵ which also contain related acids. It is a unique example where this type of skeleton has been found to occur in higher plants.

Biosynthesis of Succinic Acid Derivatives

It is well known that succinic acid represents a stage in Kreb's cycle and arises from citric acid. Therefore, it is likely that the biosynthesis of substituted succinic acids also follows the citric acid pathway, i.e. substituted succinic acids arise from substituted citric acids. As already mentioned, oxaloacetic acid (XLV) is the earlier stage which undergoes interaction with substituted acetyl CoA (XLVI) by a modified aldol condensation.

The conversion of substituted citric acids into mono-substituted succinic acids could then follow the citric acid pathway, the next step being *O*-methylation of a mono-substituted succinic acid. This is quite a feasible step as shown by Lederer²⁶.

25. Sakurai, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, 1941, 61, 108, 45.

26. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1964, 963.

An alternative route for the evolution of the roccellic acid type of compounds can be visualised, based on association of other aliphatic acid in lichens. For example, nor-caperatic acid can undergo change into a roccellic acid homologue according to the following scheme. Here *C*-methylation is not involved at any stage.

In this connection may be mentioned the results of Asano and Ohta²⁷ who were able to convert in the laboratory nor-caperatic acid (substituted citric acid) (XLVII) into α -methyl- α' -tetradecylsuccinic acid (XLIX) and α -pentadecylsuccinic acid (XLVIII) by thermal decomposition, as shown below.

This conversion follows a route different from that described earlier, based on Kreb's cycle and may represent an alternative route. There is no example known in which the laboratory method of conversion has followed the same series of reactions as in the citric acid cycle.

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